

Traditional Medical Practice and Political, Democratic Process in Nigeria: The Tiv in Focus

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Abstract

Abraham Lincoln defines democracy as government of the people by the people and for the people. However, in Nigeria this seems not to be so. Elections in Nigeria and among the Tiv in particular are characterized by violence, snatching of ballot boxes, maiming, killings, and intimidations of all kinds especially by use of charms with the view of winning. This often leads to unpopular candidates who do not have the welfare of the people at heart winning elections. Using historical and review methods, this paper attempts to discuss the use of charms popular charms in the political processes in Nigeria. It discovers that, thugs that assist their candidates to win elections use charms for protection against bullet and machete cuts. Politicians use it for protections as well as for convincing oratory of electorates. Some politicians visit shrines to make charms that will incapacitate their opponents from contesting against them. The so called 'God Fathers' use it on their God Sons to elicit loyalty and seal deals to forestall betrayal after they may have won elections. The paper amongst other suggestions states that, politicians should learn to be courageous in presenting themselves devoid of use of charms to influence electorates to elect them. Also, traditional medicine men should desist from making charms for politicians and their thugs because doing so gets wrong people into political offices which results to bad governance which affects everybody.

Keywords: Traditional Medicine, Charms, Politics, Democracy

Introduction

There has been a trend in politics among Africans and Nigerians in particular over the years; this trend has to do with the introduction of spirituality into politics in terms of seeking for prayers in churches and mosques or visiting traditional houses to seek for favours to win elections. Of particular interest to this paper is the visit to traditional medicine men to seek for charms of various kinds with the view of prosecuting elections. Whether in the north, south, east, west or central Nigeria, political thugs arrested or killed in the cause of disruption of election are usually found with charms. The charms are made for them by medicine men to protect the thugs from penetration of bullets and machetes cuts or to disappear at the appearance of any danger that is beyond their capability. Thus, the medicine men can be said to be directly or indirectly, aiding and abating rigging of elections in Nigeria to bring people of questionable characters into leadership positions. This has led to the economic challenges due to bad governance and corruption the nation has found itself in.

Politics in Tiv land is not exempted from these activities of medicine men. Election seekers find solace in traditional medical houses once they start nursing the ambition of contesting for electoral position. Even those who don't know are told by the experienced politicians to 'go to' where political contestants visit to win elections. It must be pointed out here that, not all politicians visit these places to win elections, however these ones are few. It is, therefore, very difficult to see a politician contesting for elective post without thugs that will assist him or her and these thugs arm themselves with heavy charms apart from the weapons they carry around. For Nigeria and the Tiv society to move forward, medicine men must desist from making charms for politicians and their recruited thugs to be used against the electorates to suppress their wishes of electing credible leaders.

The Concept of African Medicine

There are various aspects of African culture of which traditional medicine constitutes one of the aspects. Traditional medicine is closely knighted in Africa Religion and culture hence among Africans, all practices have religion outlook and influence. Meaning religion cannot be disassociated form the practice of medicine. Illnesses are viewed as spiritual attacks, thus treatment or cure for them must be from the spiritual angle too. This notion is emphasized by Apenda, who says, “Tiv (African) rural populace subscribes to spiritual causation of illness.”¹ Traditional medicine is essentially an integral aspect of the indigenous culture of different Africa peoples; and various linguistic groups in Africa have different terms for many classes of sickness and physical disability, medicine and healing practices as well as skilled practitioner and healers.

Attempts have been made by various scholars to explain what medicine is, for example, Guthrie describes African traditional medicine as a universal attempt to capture nature. Furthermore, he says, medicine is an attempt by man to deal with human illnesses and disease from primitive practice of preliterate man to the modern days’ complex away of specialization and treatment. The mention of primitive to modern days in the definition is an attempt to explain the dynamic nature of medicine which has undergone transformation.

The World Health Organization (WHO) in 1991 defined traditional medicine as therapeutic practice that have been in existence, often for hundreds of years and in keeping with the social-cultural heritage of different societies of the world.² WHO later viewed this definition as too narrow. Therefore, they expanded the definition to cover health practices, approaches, knowledge and beliefs, incorporating plant, animal and mineral based medicines, spiritual therapies, manual techniques and exercises, applied singularly or in combination to treat, diagnose and prevent illnesses or maintain wellbeing.³ By this definition, WHO has shown recognition for traditional medicine which it views as a health system that has helped developing nations such as Africa to meet up with their primary health care needs WHO notes that 80% of the entire population of Africa up to date still depend on traditional medicine.⁴

WHO further sums up that, traditional medicine is the sum total of knowledge, skills and practice based on theories, beliefs and experiences, indigenous to different authors whether explicable or not, used in the maintenance of health as well as in prevention, diagnosis, improvement of treatment of physical and mental illness.⁵ The above definition shows that traditional medicine is very necessary for human survival especially in developing nations where it is most needed. Sofowora on his part defines traditional medicine as: “The total combination of knowledge and practice, whether explicable or not, used in diagnosing, preventing, or eliminating a physical, mental, or social disease and which may rely exclusively on past experience and observation handed down from generation to generation, verbally or in unify.”⁶ The above definition touches on important aspects of medical practice which include knowledge care and the transmission of the ability to cure through generations which is evolutionary therefore the aspect the research is interested in. it also, demonstrates the universality of opinion embedded in the concept of traditional medicine.

Charms

The word charm is derived from French *charme* and from Latin *carme*. It simply means an object, act or words held to have magical or supernatural powers

Politics

The Greek roots of the word politic are *polis* (city) and *teche* (art, skill and method). Etymologically, politics refers to the art of governing a city.⁷ It was believed that political life as an organized mode of living started in the city and spread to the neighbourhood. In this classical sense, politics is held to be the art of organizing men in a society to live and interact with one another for the realization of their social nature.

Democracy

The concept democracy has been differently viewed by scholars. Okpaga, views it as a system of government of persons elected in representative government operating under the rule of law, where the most significant groups in the population participate in the political process and have access to effective representation in the practice of making government decision.⁸ According to Nwanko, democracy is the system of government in which the will of the majority of qualified citizens prevails or a government elected by the majority of the electorates.⁹

Traditional Medicine among Tiv

The Tiv word for medicine is *Icigh*. Just like the Tiv, other Africa groups too, have their various names for medicine. For example, the Nupe name for medicine is '*cigbe*', Yoruba call it '*oogun*' or '*isegun*' Ibos call it '*ogwu*'. There is also name for the medicine men he is referred to among the Tiv is '*or twer*' or '*or u soron kwagh*'. The Yoruba and Ibo name for medicine man is Babalawo and Dibia respectively. Generally, Africans view '*icigh*' (medicine) as power put into herbs, animal materials and other substances for healing by those with the knowledge to lay these resources of nature for their needs which could be either for good or bad purposes.

Medicines are classified into two all over Africa; there are good and bad medicines. Good medicines are used for healing, preventing and protection whole bad medicines are used for harming one's enemies. Africans, highly cherish traditional medicine in their countries as indispensable sources for health care provision.¹⁰ Thus, Adodo views traditional medicine as an aspect of human efforts to maintain health by dealing with disease and its prevention and treatment. He further says, traditional medicine has been produced since human creation.¹¹ This view is collaboration by Ife such who notes that interest in Africa traditional medicine is as old as history.¹² The biblical view traces its origin to when man became subject to illness in creation. When man disobeyed God by eating the forbidden fruit which led to his dismissal from the Garden of Eden. This led to his development of skills including the use of herbs for treatment (Gen.).¹³

Therefore, it will not be out of place to say traditional medicine emerged out of man's urgent need. Its idea came about due to men's attempt to have dominion over his physical environment; animals, diseases and indeed, natural phenomenon. African traditional medicine forms an essential part of indigenous cosmology of the different groups. A group of highly integrated universe of interacting beings and forces; essentially religious in nature and life control. Thus, wholeness among Africans is experienced of the levels of maintaining good (cordial) relationship with nature, (physical and spiritual forces). The African cosmology is essentially precarious in nature with numerous bad spirits and mystical forces said to besiege the human world. These forces and spirits attack man at every provocation inflicting him with sickness, disease, misfortune etc. Medicine arises due to threats and actual attacks of such male violent beings and forces. Persons who develop skills i.e., diviners, ritual experts and herbalists, strive to counter the menace from spiritual forces with resources available to them thereby restoring health and normalcy in man's interrelationships. Thus, it is the need to repair and maintain the intricate network of inter-relationships which the Africa cosmology engenders that makes the approval of African medicine imperative.

Eliot likens the position of traditional medicine today to that of tradition religion because religion among Africans defines health and illness and is necessary for treatment of illnesses. Also, says Africa medicine include objects or materials which exercise remote and miraculous effects on other objects; drugs for curing or preventing disease as well as recipes either magical efficacy. Therefore, African traditional medicine can be used to heal or kill, as well as secure health and fertility. Medicine will work for anyone who knows the recipe for tapping its power, and has observed all the taboos for maintaining its efficacy.¹⁴

The essential ingredients of traditional medicine are trees, soil, plants, or herbs, animal materials most times spiritual backing is needed when illness is caused by spiritual forces. Parrinder views ingredients of traditional medicine as; consisting of forces contained in and which could be extracted from the properties of human, plants, soil, herbs and animal materials applicable to human health and general wellbeing. The strength of traditional medicine is derived from the proper mixture and processing of these plants and animal materials by

medicine person who possesses knowledge of right herbs for treatment of particular ailment. The medicinal values are believed to be imparted by God into herbs and other materials which persons who possesses knowledge of their correct formula can tap into and apply for their benefit. It is in view of this that Parrinder further describes a medicine person as:

A kind of scientist, because he discovers and use the laws of the universe of both animate and inanimate (spiritual) forces. It is his belief that there are powers hidden, secret that can be tapped into, not necessarily that he can force these powers to a different purpose. But that there are laws which may be set in motion by the knowledgeable or skilled, as an electrician uses the forces of nature to create light.¹⁵

The statement above associates traditional medicine with the supernatural as necessary for treatment of most ailments. It should however be noted that some ailments are ordinary and are treated with just herbs and animal materials. It is when they defer this treatment that extra-ordinary means if sought for their cure. Ailments such as stomach ache, head ache, snake bit, fracture, snake-bit, and malaria could be treated ordinarily. However, the same ailments could also come as a result of affliction through evil forces thus requiring herbs, animal material and spiritual means to cure them. Therefore, most recipes consist not only of a mixture of herbs and other materials objects in their right proportion, but also appropriate invocation of spirits, chants, sacrifices and other associated healing rituals that are necessary for healing to take place.

In addition, Ityayar states that African traditional medicine does not only cure diseases but attends to the patient wholistically guaranteeing his wellbeing not just with his fellow humans but also the spiritual forces.¹⁶ This means that the idea of medicine in Africa goes beyond that of the western medicine which takes care of bacterial, viruses and parasites, traditional medicine reaches deep into the cause of illness beyond physical causes to spiritual causes to identify forces behind the ailment and whether the patient's action or inaction is responsible for the affliction. The patient is afterwards (after investigation) advised on the underlying cultural, political and economic issues in his or her family (community) which has predisposed the victim to the particular ill-health.

Therefore, the procedure for medical consultation under Africa traditional medical health care system is always determined by the nature and the seriousness of the patient's sickness. Among Africans, it is believed that culture and environment determine to a large extent the interpretation of health and disease and the methods of therapy to be employed in resolving this crisis in human life. Thus, Africa traditional medicine is in a wide sense regarded as a constituent part of social institution since it is bound up with the whole interpretation of life. This view is also expressed by Kalu thus; "African medicine can only be properly understood in its complete cultural context since the way in which people respond to illness or misfortune in any culture is invariably related to the whole religions and psychical frame work in which they perceive existence."¹⁷

Divination is an important tool for determining the type of medicine that can be applied to a health problem in African religion, culture. It helps to uncover the mysteries behind human problem, which also includes health. Describes divination as basic to human life because there is a common belief that the gods or spirits are in possession of secret knowledge desired by man for their own good and that their powers can be induced or imported unto man.¹⁸ Divination is viewed by Shishima as "the act of finding out what will happen in the future by means of special powers or the ability to do this." In a similar view, Moti and Wegh see divination as an investigative institution that deals with the revelation of inscrutable (mysterious) will, demands and activities of the gods as they affect the human society.¹⁹

Walker in his opinion describes aspects of divination to include all methods of future telling, card reading, crystal gazing, palmistry. He further says it is the practice of foretelling the future by means of alleged preternatural power.²⁰ This statement shows that divination covers wide range of activities and techniques aimed at revealing the past or future of humans. Mbiti in a similar view describes divination as the unveiling of the mysteries of human life which is done through the use of medicine, oracles, common Sense, intuitive knowledge and insight hypnotism and other secret knowledge.²¹ This definition by Mbiti contains concepts such as medicine, oracles, intuitive knowledge, hypnotism which are key to understanding what divination means. Middleton on his

part sees divination as means of un-covering events which could be positives or negative by supernatural means. He says “divination attempts to discover supernatural events that affect human beings for good or for evil, but which are beyond their control.”²²

Diseases and misfortune make people pose questions about their relations, motivations, choices and dispositions. Divination is therefore employed to ensure that all relevant information is brought forward before any choice and actions are undertaken. The central act of divination in African beliefs is to establish the cause of suffering with a view of finding out the solution to it, and it is a dramatic creation which may take some time to unfold. In such circumstances, choice, becomes inevitable and the ritual means of making it is provided by divination. Occasions for divination in African beliefs are universal in the sense that personal misfortune was a perpetual rather than an extra ordinary element of human existence. More importantly, African divination is inter-related with a people’s worldview.

For example, among the Urhobo of Southern Nigeria, the process of divination is one of the most essential religious practices among the people. It is through divination that they know their fate. Since Africans generally see type as being full of uncertainties considering the evil forces surrounding humans, provisions are made towards solving these uncertainties in divination which has helped the Africa people to unravel the mysteries of human life.

Divination and medicine healing are two concepts in African religion that are said to be interwoven. This is because many medicine men divine as well as heal. Divination and healing (medicine) are indispensable acts in any given Africa community. Through divination and healing (medicine) secretes surrounding are ailments renewal and the mind of duties and other spiritual forces in general are known by the interpretation of certain signs based on fixed principles or rules and once this is done then the right medicine to be applied is known and applied the healing takes place. People who carryout divination are called diviners. Describing his role, Shishima says:

The role of the diviner is crucial in determining supernatural causes of illness and affections, there are diviners who also treat illnesses. When the cause of the illness or affliction is found out or made known through divination, then the process of healing commences. Since there are no laboratories in traditional healing, the diviners serve as the laboratories.²³

The above show that divines play the function similar to modern laboratories, however, they go deeper into revealing spiritual causes of diseases which modern laboratories cannot reveal.

Traditional Medical Practice and Politics in Tivland

Traditional medical practice has had great influence on politics and politicians in general in many parts of the world especially in Africa as affirmed by..... in Nigeria too, so much has been said about the relationship between traditional medicine and politics. In Africa, medicine and religion are one because the chief priest who is viewed as a religious leader is also a medicine man and can cure diseases. Thus, when people vie for political offices, they consult leaders and members of their faiths to pray for them. Muslims go to the mosque while Christians go to the church. However, a new trend is surfacing in current practice of politics and that is the consultations of medicine men to seek for assistance to play politics. This trend has come especially because no one wants to lose elections therefore, politics in this part of the world has become violent or what people popularly refer to as “do or die politics.”

Therefore, to survive this type of politics, politicians’ resort to self -help through visits to shrines and spiritual houses to get protective charms or acquire powers to dislodge their perceived “political enemies” who are usually their political opponents. According to Orseer, he suffered health challenges when he declared his intention to contest for elections. All attempts to cure him in the hospitals proved abortive until he was taken to a traditional medical practitioner who quickly identify that it was an attack and not only treated him but fortified his body against such attacks. He further said prior to this, he never believed that one could not be harmed in this form until he experienced it personally.²⁴ Affirming the use of charms in politics, Daagba said he worked for a

popular politician as a thug. To operate effectively, he and other thugs visited traditional medicine men to acquire charms that helped to protect them from machet cuts and bullet penetration whenever they clash with thugs of a rival candidate.²⁵

Akor Chor²⁶, Bar Zuzu²⁷ and Fefa Alom²⁸, who are traditional medicine men informed the researcher that, they have been preparing various charms for different politicians in Benue. According to them, some politicians come for charms that will make them invisible or disappear at the appearance of danger. Others acquire “*gberkpugh*”, a charm for protection against gun bullets penetration and machet cuts. They also said they have charms that one can use to incapacitate his political opponent if the person insisted on not stepping down for him. On his part, Ategh Gusa said, he prepares charms for politicians that makes their would-be attackers change their minds on sighting them. According to him, when a politician he has prepared a charm called ‘*Mdoom*,’ goes to a place he has been warned not to go to, on sighting him, the same persons that planned attacking him, instead of attacking him, the charms influence them to start celebrating, hailing and chanting songs of praises to him.²⁹

Also, Akor Jagusa who claims to be a strongest medicine man in his community says he has prepared various charms for politicians that have won elections both at the state and national levels.³⁰ Narrating an incidence that took place in his area, Musan Akor said, a former local government chairman in his local government entered a cow’s belly through the anus to be born.³¹ This made him spiritually tough such that no one could harm him. (Teryila Akange, oral Interview).³² The researcher came across the said local government chairman at two different occasions, both of which he was surrounded by men dressed in blacks and carrying charms in their hands.

Also, Haanongon Posu³³ and Aseer Nongo³⁴ posited that, a senatorial candidate said in church that, the first time he was contesting for senatorial position, he was advised ‘to go to’ where people visit so as to win elections but he refused and depended on God. This made him to lose the elections. In the second attempt, he came to church on a Sunday and informed members that, he would take some time off the church activities ‘to go and do what will make him win election’. This time around he won the election (Oral Interview).

Bar Chado, in an interview said a former governor suffered two deadly spiritual attacks while serving as governor, he was advised to seek help from traditionalist to fortify himself. When he did, his political enemies could not attack his again throughout his tenure.³⁵ Also, Tersoo Allagh informed the researcher that a former governor of the state was given a walking stick that had spiritual powers to protect him and when he was angry and pointed it at a person who offended him the person will die few days after.³⁶ The researcher saw the governor with the walking stick at public functions but never knew the stick had such powers. Also, Sati Kpamor in an interview said a governorship candidate in the 2023 elections in Benue state warned his supporters against carrying charms during his campaigns, saying his victory was sealed by God.³⁷ Many other on verified claims are made of politicians’ use of traditional medical powers in politics in Tiv land.

Challenges of Using Of Traditional Medicine (Charms) in Politics

The use of charms by politicians has caused a lot of great challenges in Tiv and Nigeria in particular. This has given rise to emergence of dangerous violent groups linked to politicians in Nigeria which the politicians are using to advance their causes, for example, we have the group said to have been formed by a former Governor of Borno State, the Boko Haram and the Isis in the North and the one formed by former Governor of Benue state led by Late Terwase Agwaza popularly known as Ghana led terrorist group in the Sankera Axis of Benue State etc. who were Charmed and armed to their teeth and used by politicians for elections. But later abandoned after their principals after winning elections. This made them to turn their weapons and charms to ‘scout’ for food from the masses. Most of these people have acquired more charms and weapons beyond what their leaders knew and got for them through the monies they make from kidnappings, raiding markets, attacking villages and stealing and imposing heavy taxes on the people in villages they have captured or taken control of.

Today, just as we have so much insecurity in the northern part of Nigeria due to the activities of Boko Haram, Tiv society especially the Sankera axis has become unsecured due to the activities of “Ghana Boys.” Most

of the leaders of these groups have employed medicine as their spiritual consultants and advisors and such persons make charms for them and only members of their groups. With this, they have brought so much unrest in different parts of Tivland. Most of them have become so powerful that they have gone out of control of their founders and do not take orders from them. In fact, they have become enemies with their founders for abandoning them after using them to win elections. So, they ban them from coming to their constituencies for visits.

In Sankera, so many markets have closed down due to constant raiding of such markets by these boys on market days where they do not only steal but also kill people who attempt to resist to surrender the monies made from sales of farm produce. Sometimes, they block the roads from the markets and as traders are closing in the evening, they rob them. With assistance of agents who move around the market, they get to know those who carried out sales and visit their houses in the night and tell them the exact amount they sold their produce and request for such monies to be handed to them. If the person denies, they torture or kill him and search the house to take the money. With the help of their charms, they can enter a room and locate the exact place the money is kept. They kill owners of new motor bikes and collect them which they use for their robbery activities.

They are today, at the service of any politician that is the highest bidder. If any politician in that area is contesting for election, he negotiates with them on what he will pay for their services. They compel the electorates to vote for their preferred candidate on the day of elections. When they are arrested, these politicians secure their release and they evade justice. Due to the activities of these boys, so many persons have left those areas. Those that are still courageous to stay behind leave in fear. Businessmen have relocated away from these areas and business activities that use to be vibrant in such places are in low ebb. Schools have been short down as most of them have become homes or hiding places for these bad boys.

Recommendations

Politicians should make the saying, 'live and let's live' and 'do on to others what you wish them to do to you' their watch words by playing politics of love, respect for human lives. Medicine men should stop making charms for politicians that will want to harm or thwart the will of electorates through manipulations of peoples psyche to have their way into leadership positions. Politicians should not insist on winning elections at all cost but should allow the choice and the wills of the people to prevail at all elections. Electorates should shun any politician that will promote violence so as to win elections. The use of thugs cooked with charms and armed with dangerous weapons to forcefully win elections should be completely avoided by politicians.

The youths should resist being used by selfish politicians to destroy their future by mobilizing them to illegally help them to win elections through destructions of ballot boxes and papers but end up abandoning them when the elections are over. Such politicians are responsible for the bad governance and hardship people are facing in the country by stealing the common wealth of the people and leaving them in abject poverty.

Conclusion

The greatest dividend of democracy in the world is the respect of people's decision in a free and fair elections devoid of manipulations and violence. In Tiv society as discussed above, traditional medicine and use of charms are used to thwart the peoples wishes through manipulation of their psyche, cooking and arming thugs to force them to vote candidates against their wishes, creating violence and crises and killings of opposing candidates and supporters to scare electorates into doing their bidding. Rather than allow the people to elect good candidates, they will ensure that the people reap the benefits of politics and democracy such as good governance that will culminate into provision of good roads, hospitals, schools, industries, employment, electricity etc. Tiv society has over the years since the return of democracy in 1999 rather has experienced unemployment, bad roads, incessant political crises, terrorist and bandits' attacks said to be sponsored by politicians, frequent increase in fuel prizes and fares which leads to increase in cost of goods and services which has made life unbearable.

The wrong persons who have benefited from charms to become leaders are the reason why we are having high rate of insecurity and disrespect for rule of law through refusal to obey court orders and excessive executive

control of both legislative and judicial arm of government. Medicine men should therefore size from making charms for politicians and their thugs that will be used against the electorates to win elections wrongfully so that at all times, the best of candidates that have what it takes to move the country to the next level will be elected to take us out of this quagmire of gross economic challenges we have found ourselves in as a people.

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